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CRITICAL ESSAYS

Analysis on the use of different techniques based on three learning styles: visual, listening, and kinesthetic _____

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Abstract

This article seeks to provide data on how well the learning styles are known and how they are used in teaching methods and techniques by teachers as well as how much student learning styles are identified, a factor that leads to motivation, development of knowledge, skills and building student attitudes or improving attained results. One of the characteristics of learning related with the observation, processing and transmission of information in different ways coincides with the learning styles utilized by the student and that is identified and should be used by teachers. Their identification leads to a quality learning, which motivates every student to have positive academic and artistic achievements. The article undertakes to bring a qualitative descriptive research, where the subjects are teachers and students of the Figurative Arts and Music Department of the Jordan Misja High Art School. To validate the conclusions of this article, two questionnaires were developed and employed, which were completed by research subjects (about 100 students and 25 school teachers). Responses obtained through questionnaires validated the results obtained and the analysis performed shed light on the deficient knowledge of the teachers regarding the three learning styles. An interpretation of the responses reveals that 32.5% of teachers employ the most evident styles including other teaching techniques. Responses received through student questionnaires and interpretations made from the results of the analysis show the three styles including: a) listening learning style (62.5%), b)

visual learning style (37.5%), and c) kinesthetic style (0.70%). In conclusion, the article highlights the need to know the characteristics of the learning styles, the basis for improving student achievement as well as the quality of teaching by the using diverse teaching techniques.

Keywords: Learning styles, characteristics of learning styles, teaching techniques, motivation, positive achievement

Introduction

The changes that occur in today's society bring new needs and relationships in society, but also in the labor market, technological innovation, new human aspirations, new strategies for development, etc. (Curriculum Framework, 2014)¹. Based on this quote where many different ideas and approaches are related to the learning process emphasize the active role of students in building new knowledge, developing skills and using them throughout life. They are school institutions that help students acquire and acquire the skills, tools and processes needed to become more agile in learning and to use existing knowledge to help them acquire new knowledge. (O.C.Allan, Hunkins.P.Francis 2003)². Only in this way, students will be able to structure and organize knowledge, skills, values and attitudes, enabling their use during the learning process. This obviously requires changing the role of teachers by being more creative in the development of the process, placing the learner at the center and recognizing, adapting and using different learning styles, which should be based on different teaching strategies and methods.

Knowing and using learning styles helps the teacher to identify and highlight different ways of learning students. Also, identifying learning styles and developing them through different teaching methods and techniques would motivate them to achieve their expectations. There are many ways of learning, because what works for one student is not always effective for another, as the ways of learning and the patterns of thinking (which are partly related to sex, class, culture and intelligence, etc.) are numerous and varied. Thinking patterns help in dealing with issues or problem solving, models that require skills that match a different style of learning, which has to do with how they receive, process and remember information received or even the way how they develop it in another situation.

¹ Curriculum Framework of Pre-University Education of Albania IZHA, 2014.

² O.C.Allan, Hunkins.P.Francis. "Curricula, foundations, principles and issues". ISP, Mother Theresa Publishing House 2003.

Teachers are an inexhaustible resource in enriching the ideas and materials they use with their students, offering different alternatives and ways of mastering knowledge and learning. The planning of the teaching work and the teaching process is a phase which seeks to give the right knowledge to the students, to encourage and motivate them to be close to their needs, interests through learning styles. The learning process will be successful if the students are motivated and where each student learns in a certain way or known in the pedagogical literature as learning styles. Some students learn through perception, others learn by analyzing or reflecting, some through seeing and hearing, some learn alone, others learn in groups, some learn the whole learning content, while others break it down into smaller pieces. logic.

In addition to the above definitions for learning, there are teachers who when using strategies and techniques in the learning process, highlight their art and mastery, but also implement through learning styles different teaching techniques by approximating and combining styles of groups of students in their class. In order to achieve success in the learning process, the teacher must apply the learning styles, knowing in advance the ways in which students learn, the basis for planning the teaching work, the compatibility of learning styles and the use of teaching methods or techniques teaching depending on the styles used.

Theoretical framework

According to researchers, the classroom learning process is permeated by five elements that can contribute to student motivation which are student, teacher, content, methodology and environment (Williams and Williams, 2011)³. During this process we notice how the information is distributed in the classroom and how the same information given is then related to the students. The way of giving and receiving this information that is used continuously and regularly, and that is used to communicate with students during the learning process is called "Teaching style" (Grasha, 1996)⁴. Learning styles are created by referring to multiple theories that seek to validate their responses on different learning in different persons. Various researchers have defined learning styles as cognitive, emotional, and psychological traits of students when they interact in the classroom environment. Students with different styles try to solve problems in different ways. Studies have proven that each of us has our own learning style, style or way to receive process, remember and apply information as easily as

³ Williams, K., & Williams, C. (2011). Five key ingredients for improving motivation. Research in Higher Education Journal, 11.<http://aabri.com/manuscripts/11834.pdf>

⁴ Grasha, A. F. & Reichmann H. (1996). Teaching Style Inventory (Survey). Accessible from <http://longleaf.net/teachingstyle.html>

possible. Every teacher should first identify in their classroom the learning styles that their students possess. Among the most dominant styles are the styles of visual learning or learning learn through what they see, auditory learn through what they hear and kinesthetically learn through movement and touch.

Learning styles by different authors are named as the ways through which data, knowledge, information is obtained which are acquired and processed by the student individually. Learning styles in themselves have the element of perception (seeing, hearing, touching), feeling, thinking (acting). Therefore each student has his own way of learning. It should always be borne in mind that the best learning is done when the student learns based on interests, needs, desires and without obligations and burdens. Learning is fruitful if speaking, talking, are associated with actions, exercises and working, acting, etc. (Willingham, 2005)⁵

Characteristics of learning styles

Some of our senses help to learn, store, remember and recall information. Eyes, ears, and the impact of touch play an important role in how each of us communicates, perceives, and makes connections with others. The way we perceive, perceive, listen and act influences collaboration and communication with those we identify with the same learning style. Each student's individual learning styles are different. Every student is not only inclined to one learning style, but may need to combine styles giving them the opportunity to unfold the skills they carry.

Visual learning style is when the student acquires the learning content through the sense of sight. In this case the lesson is concretized, using teaching tools such as: pictures, graphics, paintings, colors, illustrations, dvd (where the listening style is combined). Our brain processes visual information efficiently. Thus students find it easier to recall a vivid image as a photograph than to recall what someone said or wrote. (R. J. Sternberg, 1994)⁶. Learning through sight develops from activities organized by the teacher where students are required to focus on a) observing materials set to memorize or recall an event, an event, a certain situation in the context of the learning topic, b) observation of materials set out to stimulate discussion or to verify previously acquired knowledge.

Listening learning style is when the student assimilates the learning content better and easier through the sense of hearing. Learning by listening is developed by activities organized by the teacher where students are required to be involved in a) listening to literary, musical fragments, etc., stimulating conversations or

discussions about the musical fragment they are listening to. Forms of work through listening or listening style, refers to listening to information, directing frequently asked questions or using discussion to clarify or understand the material provided. Listening style students are most successful when given the opportunity to hear information presented to them aloud. (E, E.M 1996)⁷. They choose not to keep notes and listen attentively, an action sometimes thought by teachers that they participate less than their classmates. (A, C. 1992)⁸

Students who have developed listening style are considered students who have success in group activities, where they discuss learning materials aloud with their classmates, while they benefit from reading their written work aloud. (Felder RM, 1988)⁹. Another type of learning is the inclusion of physical movements during the learning moment. Students who are part of this learning style stand out as practical students participate in learning activities, but also play a physically active role in the learning process in order to achieve the best educational outcomes.

Kinesthetic learning style is when the student assimilates learning contents actively, acting, playing, writing, drawing, etc. These students are more successful if: They act according to the learning content, b) they use body parts, they use sign language. Through learning styles, students develop different tendencies and skills, for example: interaction in different games, or group activities, artistic performance, conversations related to the topic of the lesson, etc. All three of these styles harmonize and help each teacher plan a variety of learning activities, selecting different teaching techniques. The teaching methods and techniques that are selected to meet the learning styles in are numerous, and give each student the opportunity to display and develop the potential he / she possesses within himself / herself. Good organization of the learning process means that students are placed in concrete and practical situations, where they discover, understand, create and perform through the use of diverse artistic tools.

Methodology

The article undertakes to provide answers, not exhaustive, relying on the analysis of concrete data. The study included teachers of the School with Artistic Orientation and the 9-Year School "Misto Mame" in Tirana. The questionnaires aimed to collect data and information that were answered by about 100 students of different cycles and 25 teachers of different profiles of general culture (three Albanian language teachers, three citizen teachers, one mathematics teacher,

⁵ Willingham, D. T. (2005). Do Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic Learners Need Visual, Auditory, and Kinesthetic Instruction? *American Educator*

⁶ R.J.Sternberg. (1994). Allowing for thinking styles. *Education Leadership*, pg. 36-40

⁷ E, E. M. (1996). Understanding Second Language Learning Difficultie. *American Education*, 12-20

⁸ A, C. (1992). *Canfield Learning Styles Inventory Manual*. Western Psychological Services, 10-13

⁹ Felder RM, S. L. (1988). Learning and teaching styles in engineering education. *Eng Educ*, 34-54

one physical education, five primary education , a French) as well as teachers of artistic culture figurative art branch (two graphics, two paintings, a stone-wood carving, a photograph), music teachers (a piano, a violin, a canto, an accordion). The teaching experience of the surveyed teachers varies from 5 to 25 years of teaching. The study also takes into account over 100 teaching hours observed in this school. The results that emerged from this paper will help teachers better understand the teaching style they possess and use in their classrooms. They can change or improve their learning styles, which must be adapted through different teaching techniques, create a positive climate for the learning process and for students in the classroom. Also, this paper can serve as a starting point for a more extensive study of styles that can help more in motivating students, but also a diverse application of teaching techniques by adapting to students' learning styles. The research questions we asked to be answered through the interpretation of the questionnaires were:

1. *What is the style (s) of the teacher in the study?*
2. *What learning styles do they use in their classrooms, motivating students for the most positive results?*

The data were collected through two questionnaires for teachers and students. we categorize them into 3 teaching styles. The data that were collected were collected through a questionnaire, which was created online on the Free Online Surveys page and the period in which this questionnaire was active is October. The questionnaire was completed by volunteer teachers. The collected answers were turned into styles, then these styles were analyzed through descriptive analysis. After determining the style for each participant, descriptive analysis was used once again, dividing the number and percentage of these participants into the style to which they belonged.

This paper respected the principle of anonymity because the participants who became part of this paper remained unknown in terms of their identity data. It was also respected, ensuring that no personal information about them would be made public and they were informed that the questionnaire was only intended to reveal the teaching style they used in their classroom

Findings and results

The purpose of this paper was to determine the teaching style used by the teachers of the two schools taken in the study. When asked by teachers which style of learning they belong to, grouping them based on the profile or cycle

in which he / she works, it turns out that 8 teachers (32%) answered that they belong to the listening style, 14 teachers (56%) visual style and 3 teachers (12%) kinesthetic style. To the question where the most used style of learning with students is revealed in the subject that he / she gives 16 teachers (or 64%) answer that the listening style, then comes the visual style 9 teachers (36%) and none of the participants know nor do they use kinesthetic style. Development of diverse techniques, where teachers adapt teaching techniques based on learning style, 19 of them (or 76%) answer that they use different teaching techniques but not related to students' learning styles, 3 teachers (12%) think that they adapt the teaching techniques according to the learning style that they have identified in their generally auditory and visual classes, 3 participants (12%) did not answer the question.

Based on the survey developed with students of different cycles but also different musical and figurative profiles the answers are varied and quite interesting. These results showed that depending on the situations asked they mostly used the two styles of auditory and visual learning, for example, in the question "When explaining the lesson do you remember more when?" about 55% of students belong to the listening style, then about 24% are ranked visual style students

Another interesting question that about 73% of the respondents indicated that they prefer visual learning style. This data clearly shows us that depending on the subject, questions or learning situations, students function according to different styles.

The next question is how they solve different situations or problems, about 56% of students answer that the visual tools help them, so they are more inclined to use visual learning style.

Conclusion

The purpose of this research was to determine the styles that the teachers possess who teach in different cycles and subjects of pre-university education, in two public schools "Misto Mame" and "Jordan Misja", Tirana. The results showed that 32.5% knew and identified learning styles not only in themselves but also in their students, where the visual learning style generally dominated. While 67.5% of participants were confused and failed to adapt teaching techniques in favor of learning styles. We answered the first research question by indicating that the main teaching style used by teachers was visual style. The second research question which asked whether they used or combined learning styles in their classrooms, motivating students for the most positive results. The results of the survey showed that about 67.5% of teachers were not clear about using teaching techniques conforming to learning styles for students in their class. This fact can serve as an argument for MES to provide training for teachers so that they are trained to develop knowledge about learning styles, their combination for students in the classes where they teach, making it more motivating for positive achievement through the use of different teaching techniques.

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